

Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society Ltd. - Financial Analysis of the diversified units.

Ninikala K.*

Abstract

Financial analysis of the three diversified units of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society was conducted to determine the strength and weakness of the society by establishing strategic relationship between the items in the balance sheet, profit and loss account and other operative data. The purpose of financial analysis is to diagnose the information contained in the financial statement so as to judge the profitability and financial soundness of the society. On the basis of available information profitability ratios are calculated to determine the profitability position of three diversified units ie. Dinesh food, dinesh umbrella and dinesh garments.

Introduction

In 1969, an important experiment in industrial democracy happened around the city of Kannur in the name of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Cooperative Society. They provide full employment opportunities to 12000 people directly and more than 100000 people indirectly through all their functional units. KDB's remarkable successes face two major challenges at present: ¹the integration of female workers and the need to diversify out of tobacco production. In the mid-1980s, KDB became a female-majority workforce. It might be the largest woman-owned cooperative in the world. Despite its path breaking introduction of maternity leave, KDB has not developed day care, and faces problems in maintaining productivity among women workers who are more likely than men to arrive late, leave early, or take days off for sick children. With 60% female workers in 1995, the coop had only 10% female representation on the director boards. KDB recognizes the need to improve conditions for female workers, but has not moved rapidly in this area.

*Guest lecturer, Providence Women's College, Kozhikode

Diversification also poses problems for KDB. Health awareness of the dangers of tobacco is beginning to spread in India -- paradoxically along with the rapid introduction of Western style cigarettes -- to threaten future sales of beedies. KDB has conducted extensive research into the possibilities of shifting into agro-processing. Current plans are to shift 25% of the workers into nontobacco production over the next 10 years. Already the coop has invested some of its substantial financial reserves into training workers in the manufacture of curry sauces. Meetings have been held in the production cooperatives where lists of volunteers were drawn up among workers who were willing to shift out of beedi production. Many details remain to be worked out, but it can be said that KDB is attempting a humane and democratic shift away from tobacco while maintaining the incomes of its workers. No one will be laid off.

The mission of the Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society [KDBWCCS] is the upliftment of weaker sections in the society; which is focusing on new ventures to create more employments. It started a coconut milk extraction unit during 1997, curry powder and pickle unit during 1998 and a fruit processing unit during 1999 and also started more labour oriented umbrella assembling unit during 2000. Dinesh Information Technology system (DITS) is the IT unit of KDBWCCS, started in 1999 with state of art facilities namely Dinesh Software Park, well suited for software development, Business processing and outsourcing and training centres. Dinesh Garments is a new venture setup in 2007 with advanced technology to produce export quality products.

Dinesh Ventures

1. Dinesh Beedi
2. Dinesh Food
 - Curry powder
 - Fruit Processing
3. Dinesh Soaps and Chemical Products
4. Dinesh Umbrella
5. Dinesh Garments
6. Dinesh Software

The Research problem

Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society was dealing with only dinesh beedi during the beginning period. Later on products were diversified and started dealing with non tobacco products. This study is conducted to determine the profitability position of all the diversified units of KDBWCCS. Financial analysis of the three diversified units of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society was conducted to determine the strength and weakness of the society by establishing strategic relationship between the items in the balance sheet, profit and loss account and other operative data. The purpose of financial analysis is to diagnose the information contained in the financial statement so as to judge the profitability and financial soundness of the society. But in case of KDBWCCS balance sheet is prepared for the entire society and only Trading and profit and loss account are available separately for all three units. For the purpose of comparing the financial position of three units, balance sheet is also need in the separate form. As it is not available the researcher cannot predict the financial position correctly. On the basis of available information profitability ratios are calculated.

Review of Literature

Details of available literatures are depicted here.

Mohan N (1987) conducted a study of Beedi Workers Cooperatives in Kerala. The title of the study was 'Industrial Democracy in Action'.

Mohan P (1987) in his study entitled 'Prospects and Problems of Beedi Marketing: A Case study of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Cooperative Central Society Cannanore.' was conducted to analyse the cost structure, operational aspects, and analysis of production and marketing trends and about labour benefits. It was concluded that KDBC has a good scope for expanding production, marketing and employment. Primarily recruit workers, train and enrol them as members. It has a very good system of employee's remuneration. Besides a high basic rate, the workers enjoy a host of other cash and non cash benefits such as leave wages, maternity benefits and pension. Trade unions had played a vital role in the KDBC's

management. Still the society has been facing several problems like cost over runs, threat from spurious beedis, burden of excise duty and recovery variation.

Raveendran P.V (1990) in his study entitled ‘A Study on the Art of the Financial Management in Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Cooperative Society Ltd. Kannur’ was conducted to know about the capital structure of the organisation, their overall income and return on investment over the period of the study and also about the working capital. It was concluded that liquidity position of the society was satisfactory. The main aim of the society was not making profit. It was aimed to rehabilitate the unemployed beedi workers of Kannur District. As a cooperative institution KDBWCCS Ltd had acted as a model to various Industries Cooperatives by its financial efficiency. The federal structure of the system, worker participation in management financial policy, industrial harmony, welfare facilities, purchase rebate, capital from labour etc are guide post for others. The management of the society follows a sound financial policy to make it reliant.

Thomas Isaac T M, Richard W Franke, Pyaralal Raghavan (1998) in their book named ‘Democracy at work in an industrial co-operative: The story of Kerala Dinesh Beedi’, tell the story of Democratic workers co-operative that makes hand rolled cigarettes, known as ‘Beedis’, in the unorganized sector of a fiercely competitive capitalist economy in India. For decades, beedi workers have been among the most exploited and impoverished of India’s workforce. In 1969, in the south western Indian state of Kerala, several thousand workers banded together form a worker owned beedi co-operatives. The authors argue that their skills and determination, combined with Kerala’s generally leftist political culture, allowed them to beat the odds. The co-operatives surprised the private sector beedi barons by creating an enterprise that has lasted and prospered, offering the best wages and benefits in the business while making a profit and contributing to the local economy. The authors analyze major features of the co-operatives, assessing its overall structure, worker elected management, shop floor democracy, and progress in providing a better life for its worker-owners. Tensions are also discussed including the complaints of women workers and the need for diversification from tobacco.

Frederick Abernathy, John Dunlop, Janice Hammond and David Weil in (1999) in their book review: ‘ A Stitch in Time: Lean Retailing and Transformation of Manufacturing – Lesson from Apparel and Textile Industries’ explained about the role played by the trade

unions in KDB. They have successfully served as the training grounds for leadership in the cooperative, maintained worker enthusiasm for the KDB and acted as the main feedback mechanism between management and shop floor workers. Hence the authors rightly state that the KDB is fairly well comparable to workers cooperatives in industrially developed countries. Another part of this book is 'afterwards'. It explains about the ethics of the tobacco production, the declining market for beedis and the threat of competitors from multinational companies who have taken to manufacturing small, mild cigarettes for middle class smokers in the context of increasing attacks on tobacco smoking are also discussed. The management of KDB is serious about diversification in the field rather than tobacco; the KDB has positively moved to the direction of diversification with the production of coconut curry sauce and pickled condiments manufacturing on an experiment basis.

Scope of the study

The study deals with diversification programme undertaken by Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society (KDBWCCS). The scope of the study is limited to only three units of the society. They are Dinesh Garments, Dinesh Foods and Dinesh Umbrella, as they are the leading diversified units of the Central Co-operative Society.

Objectives of the study

- To make a profitability analysis on diversified products of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society Ltd.

Research Methodology and Data Base

The present study has been designed as a descriptive one based on secondary data.

Secondary data

The secondary data, necessary for the study has been collected from various sources:

- Byelaw of the central cooperative society
- Annual reports published by the society.
- Journals
- Magazines
- Websites of KDB

Period of Study

12 years financial data are included in the study.

Tools for data analysis

For the purpose of data analysis various statistical tools and mathematical techniques were used such as:

- Profitability Ratios
- Mean
- Standard deviation
- Co-efficient of variation

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Gross profit Ratio

Gross profit ratio measures the relationship of gross profit to net sales and is usually represented in percentage. The gross profit ratio indicates the extent to which selling prices of goods per unit may decline without resulting in losses on operations of a firm. It reflects the efficiency with which a firm produces its products. There is no standard norms for gross profit ratio, it may vary from business to business but it should be adequate to cover the operating (administrative and office expenses, selling and distribution expenses) and to provide fixed charges, dividend and accumulation of reserves.

On the basis of the available information Gross profit ratio of all the three units Dinesh food, Dinesh umbrella and Dinesh garments were calculated from the year when it started its operation. Dinesh food was started during the year 1998; Dinesh umbrella was started during the year 2000 and Dinesh garments was started during the year 2007. The following table shows the gross profit ratios of three units.

Table 3.8 Distribution of Gross profit ratio in Percentage (1998-2010)

Year	Food	Umbrella	Garments
1998-99	-17.78		
1999-2000	-5.15		
2000-01	-2.97	41.17	
2001-02	-6.44	-21.09	

2002-03	-7.75	9.30	
2003-04	-20.76	62.82	
2004-05	-6.61	41.65	
2005-06	8.42	20.71	
2006-07	17.46	11.04	
2007-08	8.03	15.22	-98.68
2008-09	1.84	15.98	-204.31
2009-10	8.26	18.62	65.54
Mean	-1.9542	21.5420	
Standard Deviation	11.2561	22.7333	
Co-efficient of Variation	-5.53	1.055	

Source: Compiled and computed from the audited annual reports

From the above table it is clear that Dinesh food is having gross loss up to 2004-05, and during 2001-02 Dinesh umbrella and 2007-09 Dinesh garments is also having gross loss. But after this period they started to incur gross profit. During the year 2009-10 Dinesh garments is having high gross profit ratio. Mean of Dinesh food is -1.9542, standard deviation is 11.2561 and co-efficient of variation is -5.53 and in case of Dinesh umbrella Mean is 21.5420, standard deviation is 22.7333 and co-efficient of variation is 1.055.

Figure 1 Graphical representation of gross profit ratio

Net Profit Ratio

Net profit ratio establishes a relationship between net profit (after taxes) and sales, and indicates the efficiency of management in manufacturing, selling, administrative and other activities of the firm. This ratio is the overall measure of firm's profitability. The ratio also indicates the firm's capacity to face adverse economic conditions such as price competition, low demand etc.

On the basis of the available information Net profit ratio of all the three units Dinesh food, Dinesh umbrella and Dinesh garments were calculated from the year when it started its operation. Dinesh food was started during the year 1998; Dinesh umbrella was started during the year 2000 and Dinesh garments was started during the year 2007. The following table shows the net profit ratios of three units.

Table 3.9 Distribution of Net profit Ratio in Percentage (1998-2010)

Year	Food	Umbrella	Garments
1998-99	-35.23		
1999-2000	-48.33		
2000-01	-35.01	40.82	
2001-02	-50.50	-24.06	
2002-03	-75.90	8.03	
2003-04	-37.27	62.06	
2004-05	-6.61	36.01	
2005-06	-18.85	14.62	
2006-07	-6.61	1.64	
2007-08	-6.53	11.57	-251.68
2008-09	-8.46	9.18	-400.72
2009-10	-3.99	8.08	-32.50
Mean	-27.7742	16.7950	
Standard deviation	22.9995	23.8908	
Co-efficient of variation	-8.280	1.4225	

Source: Compiled and computed from the audited annual reports

From the above table it is clear that Dinesh food and Dinesh garments are having net loss throughout the year and Dinesh umbrella is incurring net loss only during the year 2001-02. Net losses of Dinesh garments during the first two years are very high. Only Dinesh umbrella is having net profit. Mean of Dinesh food is -27.7742, standard deviation is 22.9995 and co-efficient of variation is -0.8280 and in case of Dinesh umbrella Mean is 16.7950, standard deviation is 23.8908 and co-efficient of variation is 1.4225.

Figure 2 Graphical representations of net profit ratio

Profit/Volume Ratio

It is also known as contribution ratio or marginal ratio. It establishes the relationship between contribution and sales which has a vital importance for studying the profitability of operations of business. It reveals the effect on profit of changes in the volume. On the basis of the available information P/V ratio of all the three units Dinesh food, Dinesh umbrella and Dinesh garments were calculated from the year it started its operation. Dinesh foods were started during the year 1998; Dinesh umbrella was started during the year 2000 and Dinesh garments was started during the year 2007. The following table shows the P/V ratio of three units.

Table 3.10 Distribution of P/V Ratio in percentage (1998-2010)

YEAR	FOOD	UMBRELLA	GARMENTS
1998-99	-142.37		

1999-2000	-63.53		
2000-01	-25.31	-369.05	
2001-02	39.22	-118.97	
2002-03	9.71	15.49	
2003-04	3.19	50.69	
2004-05	6.79	42.6	
2005-06	10.56	21.31	
2006-07	4.51	12.37	
2007-08	6.20	28.31	-200.37
2008-09	-3.06	-29.79	-278.59
2009-10	7.79	8.43	-40.66
Mean	-12.1917	-33.8610	
Standard deviation	47.76	127.3130	
Co-efficient of Variation	-3.9174	-3.7599	

Source: Compiled and computed from the audited annual reports

From the above table it is clear that during first three years of Dinesh food, and first two years of Dinesh umbrella is incurring losses. After that they started having profit, but only in 2008-09 they incurred losses. But in case of Dinesh garments they have only loss, but the percentage of loss has reduced during 2009-10. Mean of Dinesh food is -12.1917, standard deviation is 47.76 and co-efficient of variation is -3.9174 and in case of Dinesh umbrella Mean is 33.8610, standard deviation is 127.3130 and co-efficient of variation is -3.7599.

Figure 3 Graphical representation of the P/V ratio

Findings

- As per profitability ratios it was found that Dinesh food unit was suffering from huge losses during the initial stages but later on they recovered from losses and started earning profit.
- In case of Dinesh umbrella unit during the initial stage itself started earning profit.
- Dinesh Garment unit was started only by 2007 and during initial period the unit suffered huge losses. Year after year quantum of losses is reducing.

Suggestions

- The Central Co-operative society has to undertake necessary measures to reduce the total cost of production of products of all the three units. Only then profitability can be increased.
- The society should try to increase the sale of all products of the three units and also try to avoid unnecessary expenses.

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